

Tools for performance monitoring and review of the CAP Strategic Plans

OBJECTIVES AND CHALLENGES

The new CAP shifts from a compliance-based model to a performance-oriented one. Consequently, Member States are now required to monitor the performance of their strategic plans (Reg. 2115/2021, Art. 128). While monitoring systems are already in place since the previous programming period (especially for compliance checks and assessment of the second Pillar of the CAP), Member States need to **enlarge the set of data collected to monitor the progress** towards several economic, environmental and social indicators. It can be challenging for Member States to identify proper data for certain indicators (especially at farm level, and for certain social and environmental indicators), whereas **existing databases are often not interoperable** and their data are not yet or smoothly available for performance review.

MAIN TOOLS ADOPTED: STRENGTHS AND WEAKNESSES

Digital Farm Book - Irrigation Calendar (PT)

The tool is a decision-making tool for **crop irrigation**. It collects information on irrigation systems to evaluate efficiency, analyse crop water requirements, and assess legal constraints. It is supported by two other tools that feed information on **agrometeorologic conditions** and irrigation to assess the crop's water status according to FAO's methodology. Outputs include detailed information about crop water requirements, irrigation timing, legal constraints, and consumption data, all of which can be accessed online.

It supports farmers' irrigation decisions, and allows farm-level data collection for legal compliance check and performance monitoring.

The tool is applicable only to monitor the irrigation water efficiency measure.

Dashboard Configuration Tool (NL)

The tool consists of a configuration feature to **monitor progress on various national-level result indicators**. It is a dashboard that compiles this data and generates a progress report. The managing authority utilises the configuration tool to monitor progress with regards the various result indicators in the Dutch context, including both economic, environmental and social indicators. Based on this dashboard, managing authorities perform quantitative analysis to assess the progress towards targets and provide qualitative explanations to the results in case certain targets are not achieved. The dashboard, therefore, **supports the drafting of the annual performance reports** required by regulation.

It allows monitoring of several results indicators (potentially all types of indicators) at national level, and can provide useful visualisations.

It provides reports and visualisations, but analyses are not automatised (i.e. they are conducted independently).

Synapse (FR)

It is a consolidated **IT architecture** capable of streamlining, auditing, and validating data for the Annual Performance Report, ensuring **uniqueness among CAP beneficiaries** across different paying agencies. Data sent by each paying agency undergoes checks for completeness, authorisation, and correctness before processing.

The tool emphasises interoperability between various management systems, minimising redundancy in data requests, and establishing a unique identifier number (GUID).

The accuracy of the data depends on the frequency of the reporting activities by the paying agencies.

